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SUMAR / CONTENTS 1/2025

Studiu privind evoluția proceselor demografice din România	3
Study on the evolution of demographic processes in Romania	12
Professor habil. Mădălina-Gabriela ANGHEL PhD	
Identificarea elementelor necesare pentru stabilirea unor modele statistico-econometrice aplicabile pentru reteritorializarea terenurilor și strategiilor agricole	21
Identification of the necessary elements for establishing of the statistical-econometrical models applicable to the reteriorization of land and agricultural strategies	29
Denis-Arthur STRIJEK PhD Student	
Managementul turismului explicat în România cu ajutorul indicatorilor turistici în turismul rural	37
Tourism management explained in Romania based on the tourism indicators in rural tourism	43
Lecturer Alina GHEORGHE PhD	
Analiza fenomenului de îmbătrânire a populației României	49
Analysis of the phenomenon of Romania's population aging	59
Professor habil. Mădălina-Gabriela ANGHEL PhD	

Making management decisions on the development of the tourism industry in the context of digitalization **69**

Associate Professor Ulviyye HUSEYNOVA PhD

Associate Professor Hecer Qafar ISMAYILOVA PhD

Akrami GASIMZADEH PhD Student

System of innovative technological development of industrial enterprises in modern conditions **80**

Associate Professor Qocayeva Elmira Mehemmed, PhD

Associate Professor Ibrahimova Sadaqat Veli, PhD

Associate Professor Mamedova Sevda Binyat, PhD

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SYSTEM OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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Abstract

This article raises the problem of achieving technological sovereignty in modern conditions: the task of providing the country with an import-independent and competitive product, for which it is necessary to create our own new technologies, conduct research and development (R & D). Achieving technological sovereignty is a complex process that includes the tools of the innovation process, R & D and technological development of production. The article presents the "symbiotic" concepts of "innovative technological development" and "system of innovative technological development", and proposes a definition of the latter. Key elements of the system of innovative technological development (SIDT) in the process of activity of an industrial enterprise in modern conditions are highlighted. It is concluded that the creation of a system of innovative technological development will allow domestic industrial enterprises to achieve the goal of technological sovereignty.

The aim of the study is to systematize theoretical and methodological provisions concerning the development of innovative activities in the context of digitalization of the economy, and to assess the relationship between the results of innovative activities and information technologies.

The subject of the study is a set of organizational and economic relations arising in the process of formation of innovative and technological development of industry. The object of the study is the process of innovative and technological development.

In conducting the research and developing theoretical positions, general and specific methods and techniques of economic research were used: calculation and analytical, grouping, analogies, expert assessments, forecasting.

The article examines the analysis and methods of the process of innovative development in industrial enterprises, the sequence of stages of the product life cycle and their stages in the implementation of new technologies (process innovation), a list of stages of creation and implementation of product, process and management innovations in modern conditions.

Digitalization means the penetration of digital technologies into most areas of economic activity - their use not only in the production of goods, but also in the organization of economic and social processes, the construction of interactions and connections. Innovative activity, mediating the creation, commercialization of new digital products and services, technologies and methods of implementing business processes, management and work with personnel, remains in the context of digitalization the type of activity through which economic entities form and strengthen competitive advantages, integrating into the digital ecosystem.

Keywords: *innovation process, system, technological development, technological sovereignty; digital.*

JEL Classification: O32, Q55.

Introduction

In the current new conditions of activity for the economy and industry, the key task is to achieve a state of technological sovereignty and implement programs for import substitution of products and technologies with their own solutions and developments. The relevance of this global goal in a tactical sense is dictated primarily by the unavailability of imported, as well as the absence of domestic solutions for the normal functioning of industries, the work of existing industrial enterprises and the implementation of development projects for the construction of new industries, as well as the breakdown of traditional logistics supply chains for import and export directions and the global transformation of sales markets. Achieving technological sovereignty is a complex process that includes the tools of the innovation process, R & D and technological development of production. Each of these three concepts is quite traditional and systematically described, but has obvious gaps, and what is more important - today there is no concept that would combine the tools within the framework of these different areas of activity: innovation, R & D and technological development. Of course, these concepts are in many ways "related", for example, R & D is often an integral part of the innovation process, and the results of R & D are implemented in production as part of technological development programs.

Literature review

Since the concept of "technological sovereignty" is directly related to the above concepts and runs like a red thread through the entire article, it is advisable to conduct a brief analysis of this concept. In the course of the review of scientific literature, it was revealed that there is no single definition of the concept of "technological sovereignty", since the term is characterized by its multifaceted nature. However, two main approaches can be distinguished among researchers to defining the concept: the first is based on the concept of "sovereignty", and then the term "technological sovereignty" is used in the meaning of the independence of domestic industries from external technologies and the ability to provide themselves with domestic products based on their own technologies [3-7]. The second approach is based on a multilateral/multifaceted consideration of the concept. For example, researcher Afanasyev A.A. [8] identifies six aspects or perspectives of the problem of technological sovereignty: economic-theoretical, system-security, institutional, production, industrial-political, and criteria-evaluation.

The researcher emphasizes that one of the possible problems of the lack of a unified interpretation of the concept of "technological sovereignty" is the impossibility of a scientific solution to the issue of assessing the achieved level of technological sovereignty. However, it is impossible to carry out in the absence of appropriate criteria and indicators of comparison. Achieving a state of technological autonomy and independence is impossible without development. "Technological development" is characterized by the mandatory condition of innovation [9]. As many domestic and foreign scientists note: "Investments in innovation are an important condition for increasing the rate of long-term economic growth" [10]. At the same time, the concept of "innovation" has many definitions [11], a significant part of which boils down to the fact that innovation is a certain novelty that has been developed and commercialized (implemented) [14]. Therefore, technological sovereignty has an obvious connection with innovation and the innovation process. It is worth noting that we are also talking about the creation of our own new technologies, that is, about the process of conducting research and development (R&D), considered within the framework of innovation management [7], since in this case the innovation does not arise by itself, but is the result of research and development and, in order to be implemented, must go through the stage of experimental design development. On the other hand, a significant part of the products that are covered by the concept of "technological sovereignty" must be physically produced products of the domestic industry and specific industries. From this point of view,

technological sovereignty is inextricably linked with the issues of technological development of industry and modernization of production, since a new innovative product must be implemented in a modernized production within the framework of using new technology and the operation of new production lines and equipment. Achieving a state of technological sovereignty automatically leads to the implementation of import substitution programs, to the development of our own unique solutions and is more high-level. An example is the country's chemical industry and related downstream industries.

The task of achieving technological sovereignty set by the country's leadership is decomposed into each industry in the form of a specific task: creating integrated chains of processing petroleum feedstock into specialty chemical products to import-substitute raw materials for final industries and produce domestic products. A "stage-by-stage" or "partial" solution to this problem, when examined in detail, does not allow achieving the goal (providing the country's economic sectors with their own sovereign product), since stage-by-stage and partial implementation boils down, for example, to replacing an imported product with a domestic one, but produced from an imported semi-finished product (predecessor). This project falls into the "import substitution" category, but does not solve the problem of technological sovereignty, since it changes the need for one imported product to the need to use another imported precursor product.

The ultimate goal in this direction is to create chains of processing integrated into domestic raw materials to final products consumed by the economy, based on domestic technologies. In this case, the state of "sovereignty" is really achieved, when there is no dependence of industries on external products, semi-finished products, technologies and solutions in critical areas - when industries are able to provide themselves with domestic solutions and technologies. Summarizing the above, we can conclude that there are a number of difficulties in correlating the concepts of "technological sovereignty", "technological development", "import substitution", "innovation", "R & D", and obvious shortcomings of the theoretical and methodological base in each of them, which does not allow these components to work within a single system leading to the achievement of technological sovereignty. Therefore, the author of this article proposes to comprehensively consider such a tool as a system of innovative technological development, the development and implementation of which can help domestic industrial enterprises achieve the goal of technological sovereignty.

Based on the identified shortage of works on the topic and the absence of methodological tools for solving the current problem, this article presents the results of a large-scale study. The most important current task today is the creation of a certain system that will achieve the goals of technological sovereignty and can be implemented at the enterprise level. Thus, this article offers a theoretical description of the system of innovative technological development (hereinafter - ITD), combining and complementing the existing tools of the subsystems of innovation, R & D and technological development. It is assumed that the implementation of such a system will become the basis for achieving the state of technological sovereignty and will maximize the final economic effect of this activity both within individual industrial companies and industries, and within the economy of the country as a whole.

Research methodology, data, results and discussions

The most important characteristic of the current stage in industrially developed countries is the transition to an innovative type of development. The innovative type of development, based primarily on the constantly increasing power, capabilities and strength of science and technology, is becoming the dominant line in the development of modern civilization. It is based on a continuous and targeted process of searching, preparing and implementing innovations, which allows for increasing the efficiency of social production, the degree of realization of the needs of society and its members, and ensuring the improvement of the life of society. Of particular importance are modern institutional changes aimed at increasing the adaptation of society to rapidly occurring technological changes, the development of methods for determining priorities in technical and economic development and mechanisms for their implementation.

The development of innovative activities in the context of digitalization of the economy is becoming a factor of economic growth, a means of strengthening the competitiveness of enterprises both within the country, at the regional level, and on a global scale. Innovative technologies play a decisive role in the creation of new goods and services, contributing to an increase in labor productivity, and, consequently, factor income and welfare of the population. The development and implementation of new information, communication, digital technologies is currently at the forefront of scientific and technological progress: the fourth industrial revolution is determined by innovative development based on the digital transformation of business processes.

This article applies a systems approach, methods of analysis and synthesis, classification and generalization, the method of monographic research. The theoretical and methodological basis of the study was the works of domestic and foreign researchers on regional and sectoral economics, as well as regulatory legal acts.

Results obtained. In order to synchronize the concepts of "innovation", "R & D" and "technological development" with the aim of integrating them into a single system of innovative technological development (SIDT), it is necessary to take into account the following main barriers.

1) The absence of a unified definition of the concept of "innovation" in the context of achieving the goals of technological sovereignty. As noted above, there are many definitions of the concept of "innovation", and if we try to generalize them, they come down to the fact that "innovation" is a certain novelty that, as a result of development and commercialization, reaches the level of final application and obtaining an economic effect. Within the framework of technological sovereignty, the task of creating one's own (sovereign) product is at the forefront, while it is not necessarily new (innovative) within the framework of the global economy. This requirement for the product to be innovative is not critical to the process of achieving technological sovereignty. The opposite situation may also arise: the product may be completely new, that is, innovative, but not critical for ensuring the country's industry. In this case, it is not a product aimed at achieving technological sovereignty. Thus, it can be concluded that the concept of "innovation" has an obvious and indirect correlation with the tasks of technological sovereignty and therefore cannot always be used as a tool for achieving a state of technological independence and autonomy. It is necessary to take this factor into account when forming the tools and elements of the created system of innovative technological development.

2) The lack of an effective methodology for managing the innovation process for industrial innovations in the context of the need to achieve technological sovereignty. The innovation process is a widely described concept [8], but it still has obvious gaps in cases of its application to modern conditions of activity. Firstly, existing approaches to defining the concept, as a rule, describe in detail the stages of the innovation process, while the primary source of innovation - the "driver" of this process, the customer - remains unclear. It is assumed that the innovation process is launched from a certain point (generation, emergence of innovation), which can be scientific institutes, researchers, startups, developers, and then goes through stages. However, industrial companies operating specific production facilities and implementing projects to build fundamentally new production facilities often do not participate in this process. At the same time, achieving technological sovereignty is a task at the level of the state, the country's economy, industries and large companies: they are the customers and "drivers" of this process. Thus, existing methodologies for managing the innovation process can work and provide an economic effect only if the issue of the customer ("driver") of industrial innovations is resolved. Secondly, scientific research is an integral part and a critical limiting stage of the innovation process, if we are talking about industrial innovations, while the process of achieving technological sovereignty itself is largely associated with the concept of "industrial innovations". At the same time, in existing methodologies for managing the innovation process, the R & D stage is only one of the stages, and insufficient attention is paid to it. In the context of industrial innovation, the R & D stage can take from 1-3 years to 10 years, until the practical application of the innovation. During such a long period, markets, macroeconomic conditions and other factors change, which affect other stages of the

innovation process and actually make the current methodology of the innovation process ineffective for the case of industrial innovation.

3) Lack of integration of production modernization and technological development processes, the role of R & D and innovation in them. The processes of production modernization and technical re-equipment are described quite well, but an obvious barrier is the fact that the role of R & D and innovation in them is minimized. This is a natural follow-up to the goal-setting of the production modernization process: its main goals, as a rule, are to increase the reliability of production, achieve product quality, comply with environmental directives and labor protection and industrial safety (OH&S) standards, but the introduction of a new (innovative product) is rarely the goal of the process of technological re-equipment and modernization of production.

In turn, this causes a two-sided problem: the processes of industrial innovation and R & D, on the one hand, and the processes of production modernization, on the other hand, are not synchronized and are not built as a single system, and often even contradict each other. For example, it is obvious that innovations in the context of production modernization can lead to a decrease in its reliability, since the process of pilot industrial production carries increased risks (both external (e.g. economic, political and legal, scientific and technical, etc.) and internal (e.g. safety of work, financial losses, information risks, risks associated with the use of labor resources, risks associated with the use of intellectual capital, etc.)).

4) Lack of a methodology for the commercialization of industrial innovations. In the context of the description of the innovation process, the key stage is the commercialization of the innovation, since it means the introduction of the product and obtaining an economic effect, however, the main emphasis in the description of this stage is not on industrial implementation, but rather on issues of markets, clients, partners, etc. These issues are certainly important, but the key aspect of industrial innovation commercialization is the engineering stage (E&D), which follows the scientific research stage (S&R). It is obvious that the process of industrial innovation commercialization is the final stage of the process of achieving technological sovereignty, but there is no serious description by researchers of this stage and its place in the system of the innovation process of an industrial enterprise.

5) Limited role of R&D and scientific research in industrial innovation. On the one hand, the task of technological sovereignty can be solved by introducing a new (innovative) product for the industry into production, but there is a related issue of the profitability of such production, which increases with the transition to products of the following stages. The key problem in the implementation of such projects is the insufficient capacity (consumption) of the Russian market, that is, the product is critically needed for the industry, but its consumption is low compared to the minimum payback capacity of production (the minimum productivity at which the project for its creation is economically efficient). This factor is a fundamental problem and a barrier, as it means that this imported product, produced at larger foreign capacities, will always win in cost and price against a domestic product produced at low capacity. The solution to this issue, based on economic prerequisites, comes down to increasing capacity and sales volumes, that is, realizing the export potential, and this, in turn, means that the product must be competitive in cost, which is determined by the technology of its production, which is ultimately a product of the R & D process. Thus, we can conclude that a critical condition for creating a system of innovative technological development is the integration of the R & D process, ensuring the creation of not only an innovative product for the domestic industry, but also the ability to win the competition in foreign export markets. The above barriers are not the only ones, there are other shortcomings in the existing systems and methodological entities of innovation, R & D and technological development, which do not allow the existing tools to be automatically harmoniously and effectively combined into a single system. Therefore, theoretically, the state of technological sovereignty cannot be achieved. Hence the need to develop such a system that will ensure synergy and economies of scale, will increase the chances of releasing a product that is competitive in cost and in demand by the market.

Taking into account the above, the concept of the "System of Innovative Technological Development" (SIDT) proposed by the author of this article, namely the further application of its

principles in practice, is intended to help solve an extremely urgent problem in modern conditions - achieving a state of technological sovereignty. This will also fundamentally solve the issues of import substitution and will allow achieving a fundamentally higher economic effect from innovations within individual industries and the economy of the country as a whole. In addition, the implementation of SIDT will avoid the above barriers.

Firstly, unlike the processes of innovation management, within the ITR system, the primary goal will be the creation of a domestic sovereign product and/or technology, regardless of the degree of its innovativeness, but based on the need to create its production within the country or region.

Secondly, the fundamental starting point in the ITR is the strategy of technological development (of the country, region, industry and company), which is absent within the description of the innovation management process. Therefore, this element of the ITR is innovative and extremely important, since it is the starting point for launching the further process of creating innovations and R & D.

Thirdly, within the ITR, the processes of R & D and technological modernization of production are synchronized. It is important to note here that the modernization of production within such a system should meet the goals of technological sovereignty of the industry, country, company, and not local (point) goals to which modernization is usually aimed. This will make it possible to use the results of R & D, and this is the difference from the approach in which technological modernization is based not on scientific developments, but on existing foreign technologies. And finally, within the framework of the ITT, a system/process of commercialization of industrial innovations is being created, which has been poorly studied by domestic economists and is associated with many uncertainties.

It is worth noting that the created system of innovative technological development should be adaptive and flexible, that is, applicable to companies of any type from various industries. This imposes certain requirements on the components of the ITT, each of which should be described in sufficient detail to be practically implemented and remain flexible to be able to adapt it to the real conditions of the industry and the company. Thus, the following key components (elements) of the system of innovative technological development (ITD) can be identified:

1) Strategy for technological development of companies, industries and technological sovereignty. As noted above, there is a fundamental problem of the "customer of innovations", which in practice leads to low efficiency of the innovation process as a whole, especially in the field of industrial innovation. As a rule, innovations are initiated by research teams and developers who are not integrated into the development strategy of either individual companies or the industry as a whole, and what is even more important is that innovations are developed and implemented not in predetermined areas, but based on accumulated scientific reserves, which ultimately makes innovations unclaimed within real companies and industries. The strategy of technological development is the first key element of the SIDT, the creation of which will allow, at the level of companies, the industry and the country, to determine the key areas for achieving technological sovereignty in the form of specific products and technologies to be developed within the framework of innovation and R & D processes. Thus, the creation of a strategy for technological development is the starting point of the process of achieving technological sovereignty and the accompanying processes of innovation and R & D. The development of such strategies, in turn, will provide the basis for generating a strategy for the technological development of the industry, and the comparison and unification of industry strategies will lead to the creation of a strategy for the technological development of the country as a whole. Such a system of level synchronization of strategies will create a basis for the effective allocation of state support for scientific and technological development projects of the country. This will allow targeted support for the most capital-intensive stages of the industrial innovation process, namely the stage of pilot industrial development of technology, which requires the creation of an expensive, but often non-recoupable, pilot industrial installation for the purpose of scaling it up and moving on to the design and construction of an industrial installation.

2) The process of searching for technologies and building a technological landscape. Continuing the logic of the previous point, if the directions of technological development at the strategic level are defined, the next necessary step is not always the beginning of development based on the existing fundamental scientific groundwork, namely, building a technological landscape by assessing and searching for technologies. As a rule, within the framework of domestic science, there are accumulated scientific groundworks in all areas, but there are two fundamental problems: firstly, the competitiveness of such technologies is often not high, secondly, in some cases it takes up to 7-10 years to complete the R&D stages and bring the innovative product to the commercialization stage, and the product is needed today, and this is the point of synchronization with the tasks of technological sovereignty. Building a technological landscape and targeted selection of technology is a key element of the SITR, as it allows you to consciously select those areas in which the created product will be competitive and brought to the market within the specified time frame. The presence of this element in the ITS makes the system itself effective for achieving the goals of technological sovereignty. Thus, now the preceding stage within the ITS is the search for existing technologies and ways to implement innovation (R & D) in the fastest possible way.

3) Methodology for assessing and selecting projects and methodology for portfolio management of ITS projects. The task of technological sovereignty is global, and its solution occurs in the context of a lack of resources - financial, time, human. It would be impossible for one company or industry to develop and implement all ITS projects, in connection with which the key element of the ITS is the ITS project portfolio management system and the project assessment and selection methodology, which together allow you to determine priority projects for implementation based on clearly developed assessment criteria, and carry out system management of the total portfolio of ITS projects. For this purpose, it is proposed to create a system for prioritizing and compiling a project portfolio based on three groups of criteria: feasibility (from TRL and own competencies), potential maximum economic effect and compliance with the strategy of technological development. This mechanism allows for the initial selection of projects that correspond to the strategy and their ranking in a two-dimensional matrix of "feasibility - maximum potential effect".

4) Organizational design, management mechanisms and R & D management processes. Traditionally, R & D processes are carried out within research institutes, but in modern conditions this model does not allow for quick results in the field of creating new products for a number of reasons, since there is no synchronization at the strategic level of the research directions of institutes with the tasks of technological development of industrial companies. Also, the lack of qualified specialists, scientists, researchers within the industrial companies themselves does not allow them to be qualified R & D customers. The solution to this problem lies in the creation of large industry development centers within one or several key industrial companies, which would concentrate the efforts of scientific researchers, engineers, technologists, and commercialization specialists. This will allow creating the opportunity to work on the full cycle of the engineering and technical system within such centers. At present, observing the activities of scientific organizations, one can notice that many of them are responsible for the fundamental stage of development, while the commercialization stage is given little attention or is ignored. At the same time, industrial enterprises and large corporations do not have the tools to implement innovations, since there are no necessary mechanisms and relevant practices, and, therefore, no personnel capable of conducting fundamental research following the example of scientific organizations. Therefore, within the framework of the SITR of enterprises, it is proposed to create centers (structures) that are responsible for both engineering and commercialization of innovations, which did not exist before. Scaling such a SITR model to large corporations will increase the overall effect of implementing innovations in the country several times.

5) New hybrid methodologies for managing engineering and technical projects. Industrial innovation projects have a clearly defined specificity: their successful implementation is possible only after going through all stages of the innovation process, R&D and commercialization, which takes

several years, and at different stages of implementing engineering and technical projects, the specificity of the project itself changes fundamentally. At the early stages of the engineering and technical process, the degree of uncertainty is very high, costs are low and the optimal solution is to use flexible project management systems, such as Agile. Thus, for the successful functioning of the engineering and technical project as a whole, it is necessary to create a hybrid management methodology with its own toolset that changes during the transition from stage to stage. Thus, a new approach and toolset for project implementation are proposed, starting with flexible methodologies and smoothly moving to the RMR methodology from the engineering stage.

6) The process of engineering new technologies - recreating the function of industry institutes. Upon successful completion of the R&D stage, the engineering and technical project moves to the R&D stage, within which the necessary element is the engineering of the new technology. This task was previously solved by industry institutes, but in modern conditions the task is much broader: it is necessary to create engineering centers capable of developing engineering, design and technological solutions using proprietary technology that has no analogues, producing initial design data at the output, which are the input data for the beginning of the design process carried out by design institutes.

7) Methodology for commercialization of industrial innovations. As noted above, the commercialization stage is described within the framework of the created methodologies of the innovation process, however, with regard to industrial innovations, it is necessary to develop a separate methodology that would take into account all optional possibilities for implementing technologies within the industry as a whole at specific production facilities, not limited to the developer's site only, and would allow for the formation of the fastest effective mechanisms for implementing technology for the purpose of producing and releasing the product to the market. We are talking about the commercialization of industrial innovations. The very concept of "commercialization of industrial innovations" comes down to industrial implementation within the framework of production. Accordingly, such commercialization includes the engineering stage, which is not implied in the simple commercialization of innovations, and integration into the process of technological modernization of production [8].

8) The system of licensing, technology transfer and intellectual property management. One of the global areas of commercialization of industrial innovations is technology transfer through licensing, which provides the country and industry with the opportunity to obtain a product, and for the developer company - to achieve an economic effect from innovations. As part of the development of this element, it is necessary to create a separate pricing methodology in the market of technological licenses that are a product of industrial innovations. The most important element of the SITR is also the creation of an end-to-end intellectual property management system at all stages of the life cycle of an ITR project, based on the concept of "patent protection strategy". The creation of this element will ensure full protection of the developed solution in the technology market when implementing technology transfer transactions.

9) The mechanism for the creation and management of a managed innovation ecosystem. One of the key elements of the SIDT is the creation of innovation ecosystems (IES) or ecosystems of partners of a new type, which would allow to achieve industrial innovation goals faster and maximize the economic effect from the implementation of new projects, thus solving the problem of technological sovereignty. It is worth noting that the very concept of IES is quite well described and studied in the literature, but in modern conditions, current IES are not effective enough to achieve the goals of technological development of companies and industries, since IES participants have a significantly lower development speed, are not synchronized with each other (their process is not built as a system and covering the entire cycle of ITR projects). In this regard, it is necessary to create a new, separate type of ecosystem of partners, which, within the framework of the SIDT, would be able to create the final sovereign technological product in the shortest possible time due to the coordinated action of its participants at all stages of the SIDT life cycle.

10) Center (entity) and mechanisms of SISTR management. The most important summarizing component of SISTR is the entity managing the system, which carries out the management process itself and is responsible for achieving the final result - the implementation of the goals of technological development. The organizational design of this Center can be different and is adaptive, but its key elements are the presence of structures that implement the work of the SISTR elements described above, this is the fundamental principle laid down in the organizational design of the SISTR management center. Within the existing innovation management centers (R & D) in large corporations, a number of functions are missing, for example, departments responsible for the commercialization of industrial innovations, engineering, scouting. Within the SISTR, it is proposed to transfer the management of the system to departments implementing the strategy of technological development of the enterprise, which will ultimately ensure a full cycle of the innovation process: from strategy to implementation.

11) System of training and development of personnel for SISTR. The most important component and fundamentally necessary basis, which runs through all stages of the ITS, is the personnel training and development system, which should be built based on the functionality and tasks at each stage of the ITS. This system is based on the formation of competency profiles of specialists capable of implementing tasks within the framework of the ITS management center.

Conclusions and prospects for further research

Thus, this article proposes the concept of an innovative technological development system (ITD) - a development system consisting of interrelated elements:

- a strategy for technological development;
- a process of searching for technologies and building a technological landscape;
- a methodology for portfolio management of ITS projects;
- organizational design, management mechanisms and R & D management processes;
- hybrid methodologies for managing ITS projects;
- a process of engineering new technologies (recreation of the function of industry institutes);
- a methodology for the commercialization of industrial innovations;
- a system of licensing, technology transfer and intellectual property management;
- a mechanism for creating and managing a managed innovation ecosystem;
- a center (entity) and mechanisms for managing the ITS;
- a system for training and developing personnel.

The elements that make up the ITS system and the tools proposed within their framework are intended to assist enterprises in the processes of:

- searching for existing technologies and ways to implement innovations;
- implementing innovative products and/or technologies based on the goals of industry strategies;
- selecting projects that correspond to the strategy of technological development;
- integrating the engineering stage into the ITS cycle and into the process of technological modernization of production;
- ensuring a full cycle of the innovation process: from strategy to implementation.

Thus, the implementation of the system of innovative technological development at industrial enterprises will allow achieving the goals of the strategy of technological development and will fundamentally affect the country's economy as a whole through the introduction and launch of its own new products and technologies on the market, which will thus solve the problem of innovative development of the economy.

References

1. Dunenkova, E.N., Onishchenko S.I. (2023). Technological Sovereignty: Innovative Development of Industries. *Innovations and investments*, 4, 15-18
2. Afanasyev, A.A. (2023). Technological Sovereignty: on the Question of the Essence and Mechanism of Achievement. *Trends and Development Prospects*. 2023. pp. 28-32

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3. Kvint, V.L., Novikova I.V., Alimuradov, M.K., Sasaev, N.I. (2022). Strategizing the Technological Sovereignty of the National Economy. *Management Consulting*, 9, 57-67. DOI: 10.22394/1726-1139-2022-9-57-67
 4. Dolganov, N.V., Dolganova, N.A. (2017). Problems of Managing Scientific and Technological Development of Industry and Enterprises. *Trends and Development Prospects*, 389-394
 5. Kulakova L.I. (2023). Methodology for Regulating the Innovation Policy of Entrepreneurial Structures Within the Framework of the National Innovation System in Conditions of Uncertainty, Available at: <https://elib.spbstu.ru/dl/2/r23-37.pdf/en/info>
 6. Antipov, A.A. (2017). Modern Problems of Innovation: Educational Manual. St. Petersburg: ITMO University, 89 p.
 7. Nikulin, M.V. (2024). Technological Development of Oil refining: Petrochemistry, Small-Scale Chemistry, Engineering and Commercialization. Materialy XVI Scientific and Practical Conference "Current Challenges of the Oil and Gas Chemical Complex", Moscow, 16-17
 8. Eminov, A., Gojaeva, E., Gutium, T., Badalov, B., Guliyeva, G. (2024). "Green economy" as a means of ensuring eco-friendly agricultural production. *Reliability: Theory & Applications*, 19(SI 6 (81)), 1133-1144
 9. Gojaeva, E., Adilova, N., Chobanli, E., Gutium, T. (2024). Green Economy as the Basis for Innovative Environmental Sustainable Development. *International Conference on Smart Environment and Green Technologies*, April, 465-472, Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland
 10. Babayeva, S. et al (2024). Green Innovation as a Factor of Economic Growth. Development. *International Conference on Smart Environment and Green Technologies*, April, 523-532, Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland
 11. Gutium, T., Gojaeva, E., Huseynova, S. (2023). Social exclusion and poverty in the European Union and candidate countries. *Cogito Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, XV 2, 124-145
 12. Asenova Z.T., Azytkanova, S.A. (2018). Modern Trends in Project Management. *National Association of Scientists*, 37, 59-62